

Beam Diagnostics for Cyclotrons

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How to spend only 45 minutes on beam diagnostics for cyclotrons?

- option a) take few examples of diagnostics inside a cyclotron (e.g. radial probe, phase probes)
discuss it in depth
- option b) give an overview of diagnostics inside a cyclotron
discuss operation in different types of cyclotrons/for different applications
- option c) give an overview on diagnostics in general (methods, monitors, tasks)
with some weight on cyclotron & its injection lines

here I follow mostly option c), **but**

- nearly nothing about details / technical issues / the „art of construction“ / electronics
- just to tell what is around in the field
(and still this are only examples, many other realizations exist)
- references to literature are given as a starting point
- more slides/information than digestable immediately
→ don't try to read everything now
- it is not really a lecture, but I hope you can profit from it

Beam Diagnostics for Cyclotrons

- A) introduction: environment / tasks / beam parameters
- B) effects used for transversal profile measurement: basic physics/techniques
- C) diagnostics along the beam path: practical examples mostly from PSI's Injector 2
 - ion source & injection line: matching the beam to cyclotron acceptance
 - injection, central region: beam shaping & current set, betatron oscillation alignment
 - acceleration: adjustment of magnetic field and RF fields
 - extraction: turn separation & efficiency
- D) transversal information (in cyclotron): radial probes (for high/low current)
- E) longitudinal information (in cyclotron): phase probes, bunch shape, ...
- F) beam losses & beam halo: protection / insight

beam diagnostics is a very large field

- used at different machines: linear & circular accelerators for electrons, protons, hadrons
- many physical effects are used to sense the beam
- a large variety of technical realisations in many labs

beam diagnostics *for cyclotrons* is a subset

- not all techniques usable due to special boundary conditions
 - specific tasks in cyclotrons
 - different types of cyclotrons have different needs
- adapted diagnostics

and well-established

- nearly all principle diagnostic techniques used today were already present in the 1970s
 - since then improvement mainly in detail
 - better sensors
 - better electronics (analogue & digital)
 - (better drives)
- improved diagnostics
(but also improved machines around it)

A wealth of literature on beam diagnostics

Proceedings Cyclotron Conferences 1959-...,

Beam Diagnostics Conferences BIW 1989-2012, DIPAC 1993-2011, IBIC 2012-...,

Accelerator Conferences PAC, EPAC, APAC, IPAC, LINAC, HB

→ JACoW <http://www.jacow.org/> (not all from the beginning)

(Brandenburg et al. DIPAC03, Dölling DIPAC2005, ...)

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d03/papers/CT10.pdf> http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/d05/TALKS/ITTA02_TALK.PDF

Journals: Rev. Sci. Instrum., Phys. Rev. ST-AB, Nucl. Instr. Meth. A, JINST, ...

including overviews

JUAS (e. g. Forck 2011) http://www-bd.gsi.de/conf/juas/juas_script.pdf

CAS (e. g. Wittenburg/Braun/Bravin et al. 2008, 2010) <http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/France-2008/Lectures/Dourdan-lectures.htm>
<http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/Bilbao-2011/Lectures/BilbaoLectures.htm>

CARE-Conf-08-033-HHH http://adweb.desy.de/mdi/CARE/Bad_Kreuznach/Reports/ABI-Workshop_Proceedings_all.pdf

Wittenburg HB2006, Raich DIPAC2005, Plum BIW04 p. 23, ...

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/abdwbb06/PAPERS/TUAZ01.PDF> http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d05/TALKS/ITMM01_TALK.PDF

and overviews for cyclotrons

Mackenzie CYC78, Clark CYC66, Olivo CYC75, Dölling CYC10

p. 2312

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/c66/papers/a-002.pdf>

p. 331

http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/Cyclotrons2010/talks/wem2cio04_talk.pdf

In late 1930, Lawrence's student, **Stanley Livingston**, built a "4-inch" version in brass. Clear evidence of **magnetic field resonance** was found in November, and **in January 1931 they measured 80-keV protons**.

Ions were produced from the residual gas by a heated filament at the centre. Note the liberally applied red sealing wax for vacuum tightness - and Glenn Seaborg's left hand.

from M.K. Craddock, Lecture "Introduction to Particle Accelerators", see also CYC10 p. 1, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/Cyclotrons2010/talks/mom1cio02_talk.pdf

boundary conditions from different cyclotrons

property of cyclotron

*impact on boundary conditions
for diagnostics in cyclotron via*

*affected
requirement to diagnostics*

high/low beam current

thermal/radiation load, activation
direct/indirect
shielding difficult

machine protection
activation control
reliability/maintainability

high/low beam energy

penetration depth, cross sections

protons/H⁻/heavier ions

residual gas pressure

external/internal source

available space, magnetic field

separate sectors/compact

RF nearby

normal/superconducting

standalone/coupled machine

turnstructure: separated/not

different techniques

single-/multispecies

frequentness of setups
(particle identification)

downtime critical/not

reliability/maintainability

unique/series model

amount of diagnostics

this is different in cyclotrons

JAEA
930 AVF
cyclotron

phase probe signal cables damaged by RF
after introduction of Flat-Top system of
few kV, 80-100 MHz

(now still noise is picked up and hence
phase measured with Flat-Top off)

all pictures from S. Kurashima, JAEA

a difficult environment

radial view into PSI Ring cyclotron
 RF on (~ 3 MW), magnet on (~ 1.7 T)
 beam off
 $\sim 10^{-6}$ mbar

trim coils

thin plasma
 in sector magnet
 at lower machine radii
 (always present?)

impact on
 electrostatic septa
 probe measurements?

pictures from R. Kan, PSI, see also D. Goetz et al., CYC10, p. 341, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/Cyclotrons2010/talks/wem2cco03_talk.pdf

- for **machine safety** (prevent the beam from melting something) ms
 e. g. collimator with current measurement
- for **machine stabilisation** s
 e. g. closed loop beam current stabilisation by adjustment of ion source arc current
- for machine **setup & tuning** 1 day ... 1 week
 e. g. phase measurement for adjustment of main coil current
- at **beam development** (finding new settings, with or without changed hardware)
- for **error search** 1 month
- only at **commissioning** once
 e. g. finding trim-rod settings for centered beam

for all tasks beam measurements should deliver the ϵ of information
 which is still needed in spite of

- good design due to theoretical understanding & simulations & field mapping & experience
- suitable operation due to -“-
- good stability of machine components and environment
- reliable machine components

(these fields have improved much over the years, but the demands also increase)

B) effects used for transversal profile measurement

(depending on geometry also for full beam or beam halo,
also part of emittance measurement)

(effects / methods usable for beam measurements in general)

information	configuration	usable effect/device	usable A) for machine safety B) permanently C) for tuning D) at setup E) for error search F) only at commiss.	destructive	able to work inside cycl.	alrdy. used inside cycl.	usabl. at good vacui	beam current range (assumed DC beam at 70 MeV, 10 mm diameter, to be determined more precisely)	common names
1D: 1D-profile 2D: 2D-profile Dz: long. prof. Pos.: position E: energy C: full current									
beam self fields									
Pos, Dz, C	pickups	comparison of capacitively or inductively coupled RF currents	A B C D E	no	x	x	x	nA ... A	pickup, BPM, phase probe
C, (Dz)	transformer	DC or AC current transformer, wall current monitors	A B C D E	no	?		x	nA ... A	DCCT, ACCT, wall curr. m.
1D, C, (Dz)	"wire"	electron (or ion) beam probe	B C D E	no			x	mA ... >A	electron beam probe
1D, C	residual gas	residual gas ions (with beam space charge field)	?	no			(x)	mA ... >A	[21]
direct beam current									
1D (/+Dz), C	in full beam	probe finger: current of stopped beam fraction (/+50Ω-readout)	D E	yes	x	x	x	nA ... uA	radial probe/Faraday cup
<1D	beam edge	collimator: -"	A B C D	"no"	x	x	x	pA ... mA	collimator
1D, C	wire	wire: -"	C D E	~no	x	x	x	-	wire scanner
heating of introduced solid matter									
1D, C	in full beam	probe finger: direct (or cooling water) temperature measurement	D E	yes	x	x	x	nA ... uA	calorimeter probe
<1D	beam edge	collimator: -"	B C D	"no"	x	x	x	nA ... mA	
1D, C	wire	vibration resonance shift	C D E	~no	?		x	pA ... uA	vibrating wire scanner
1D	wire	wire: resistance	C D E	~no	x		x	uA ... mA	
E, C	in full beam	probe finger: 2 thermocouples + degrader	C D E	yes	x		x	nA ... mA	[22]
2D, C	in full beam	metal/carbon foil: thermal light emission/thermionic emission	A B F	~yes	x	x	x	uA	[23, 6]
1D	wire	wire: -"	C D E	~no	x	x	x	uA ... mA	
changes to introduced solid matter									
2D	in full beam	paper/Kapton/Mylar darkening, metal foil burn	F	yes	x	x		nA ... uA	foil burn
2D, C	in full beam	radiochromic film	F	yes	x	x		<pA ... nA	
2D, C	in full beam	foil activation analysis, autoradiograph	F	yes	x	x	x	pA ... uA	autoradiograph
secondary particles from introduced solid matter									
1D, C	wire	wire: secondary emission current, direct measurement	C D E	~no	x	x	x	pA ... mA	wire scanner
<1D, C	beam edge	foil: -"	A B C D E	"no"	x	x	x	pA ... uA	SEM foil, aperture foil
2D, C	in full beam	foil: secondary emission current + pulling + 2D-electron detector	A B C D E	~no	x		x	pA ... uA	
1D, Dz, C	wire	wire + detection of scattered or secondary particles	C D E	~no	x	x	x	nA ... mA	time structure m./wire scanner
Dz, C	in full beam	foil + detection of scattered or secondary particles	C D E	~no	x	x	x	nA ... mA	time structure measurement
2D, C	in full beam	scintillating screens + 2D-light detector	C D E	yes	x	x	x	pA ... uA	scintillator screen/viewer probe
1D, Dz, C	"wire"	scintillating fibres + (external) PMT	C D E	~no	x		x	<pA ... nA	
Dz, C	in full beam	scintillator + (external) PMT	C D E	yes	x	x	x	<pA	time structure measurement
<=2D, Dz, E, C	in full beam	silicon/diamond bulk/strip/pixel detector	C D E	yes	x	x	x	<pA/<nA	silicon strip detector
secondary particles from introduced dense gases									
1D, C	"wire"	coaxial ionisation chamber	C D E	~yes	x		x	<pA ... uA	
1D, C	in full beam	ionisation chamber + strip-electrode readout (in beam/not)	(B) C D E	yes/~yes	x		x	<pA ... uA	strip ionisation chamber
2D, C	in full beam	ionisation chamber + pixel-electrode readout (in beam)	C D E	yes	x		x	<pA ... uA	pixel ionisation chamber
1D	in full beam	proportional chamber	C D E	~yes			x	<<pA ... nA	wire chamber
1D, 2D, C	in full beam	GEM	C D E	yes	x?		x	<<pA ... nA	GEM
secondary particles from residual or thin gas									
2D, C	gas curtain	beam induced fluorescence + (external) light detector	A B C D E	~no				nA ... >A	gas curtain
1D, C	residual gas	beam induced fluorescence + (external) light detector	A B C D E	no	x	x	(x)	mA ... >A	BIF monitor
1D (2D), C	residual gas	res. gas ions/electrons with external fields + strip(/+energy) det.	A B C D E	~no	x	x		uA ... A	residual gas profile monitor

Dölling, CYC10 p. 344, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/Cyclotrons2010/papers/wem2cio04.pdf>, see also Koziol, CAS2000 p. 154, <http://cdsweb.cern.ch/record/425460/files/CERN-2005-004.pdf>

- stopping material thick enough? → for protons projected range <http://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/Star/Text/PSTAR.html>
→ for ions e. g. <http://www.srim.org>, <http://geant4.cern.ch>
- signal altered by secondary electron emission at surface, SE energy mostly around 2 eV, yield >1 at low beam energies
for absolute measurements: suppression with electrode at ~100 V (electrode not to be hit by beam!)
or with permanent magnets → Faraday cup
for most applications: better to let SE escape or to pull them away
- signal altered by stray particles (residual gas ions, external SE)
- with magnetic fields & beam space charge → path of SE or stray particles difficult to predict (ExB-drift, ...)
- if directly water cooled: at very small currents measurement can be disturbed by water conduction

wires or strips
or full foil
(fill factor, thickness
→ destructive or „not“)

- at higher energies: ions not stopped,
signal only from SE

- optional pulling of SE by external electrodes or adjacent foils
(foils also block stray particles, filtering of high voltage needed)

- SE-yield depends on surface material
& structure & contamination,
ion species & energy

- SE-yield depends on irradiation history,
Titanium is good [Ferioli, Jung, DIPAC97, pp. 168-170](#)

- signal is very fast (<ps)
and linear (large dynamic range)

Kramer et al., DIPAC2007, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d07/papers/wepc03.pdf>

according to Badano et al., DIPAC03/07

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d03/papers/CT09.pdf>

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d07/papers/wepc20.pdf>

- ~non-destructive
- fast
- sensitive
- fragile foil? → careful venting of beam line

other variants:

Kruglov et al., Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A 441 (2000) 595-604

Shapira et al., Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A 454 (2000) 409-420

very fast:

http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/HB2010/talks/weo2a02_talk.pdf

- scattering at high and low energies
(at not too low energies ~according to Rutherford formula)
- creation of secondaries at higher energies
- very large dynamic range (if background radiation low, coincidence technique)

Raich, DIPAC05,
http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d05/TALKS/ITMM01_TALK.PDF

instead of moving wire or grid

- light emission spectrum (to be compatible with light detector)
- decay time ns >s
- doped bulk anorganic material (ceramic, glass, crystal → rugged)
 - doped plastics
 - thin coating on metal (phospor powders → fragile)
 - thin layer in plastic (intensifying screens, Kodak Lanex = P43)
- image broadening by light scattering → thin screen
- saturation, thermal damage, radiation hardness
 - for limited beam current

http://www.proxitronic.de/datasheets/20091001_ebv.pdf

Type	Composition	Light Emission			Decay Time	
		from	to	Maximum typically at	Color	Decay of Light Intensity
P 43	Gd ₂ O ₂ S:Tb	360 nm	680 nm	545 nm	green	from 90 % to 10 % in 1 ms, from 10 % to 1 % in 1,6 ms
P 46	Y ₃ Al ₅ O ₁₂ :Ce	490 nm	620 nm	530 nm	yellow green	300 ns, 90 μs
P 47	Y ₂ SiO ₅ :Ce,Tb	370 nm	480 nm	400 nm	blue white	100 ns, 2,9 μs

<http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/France-2008/Lectures/Bravin.pdf>

Jung et al., DIPAC03, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d03/papers/IT03.pdf>

Gütlich et al., DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tupb04.pdf>

DIPAC11, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/DIPAC2011/papers/mopd57.pdf>

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/DIPAC2011/papers/mopd53.pdf>

Re et al. PAC2005, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p05/PAPERS/RPAT002.PDF>

effects on foils & films

paper/Kapton foil coloration

- colouring by beam heating
- readout with scanner
- not linear

radiographic film

- like photographic film
- development needed

track-etch foil

- tracks in nitrocellulose
- etched
- counted

radiochromic film

- optical density increases with dose
- dose range 0.001 ... 100 Gy
- easy to use (no light sensitivity, no development)
- readout with flatbed scanner
- can be calibrated

<http://www.gafchromic.com/>

Mumot et al., PTCOG46,
[http://ptcog.web.psi.ch/PTCOG46/May%202022,%202007,%20morning/\(22\)-\(5.22\)\(9.00\)M.Mumot\(Dose%20distribution%20measurements\).pdf](http://ptcog.web.psi.ch/PTCOG46/May%202022,%202007,%20morning/(22)-(5.22)(9.00)M.Mumot(Dose%20distribution%20measurements).pdf)

Optical Density - Dose Calibration Curve
for a Gafchromic EBT film (lot # 36076-0021)
irradiated with protons

Bues, PTCOG45, http://online1.ispcorp.com/_layouts/Gafchromic/content/presentech/pdf/14MBues.pdf

foil activation

- activation of metal or polyethylene foil (if ion energy above a few MeV)
- contact radiography to
 - imaging plate (semistable excitation) read-out with laser scanner (deexcitation observed with PMT) few $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ detectable, 50 μm resolution \rightarrow very large dynamic range
 - radiochromic film \rightarrow large dynamic range
- linear

Clarke et al., NIM A 585 (2008) 117-120
Tamburella, Giles, NIM B 266 (2008) 4678-81

Avila-Rodriguez et al., Applied Radiation and Isotopes 67 (2009) 2025-2028

ionisation chamber

instead of moving wire

- signal enhanced by ion pair generation $\eta = \text{stopping power} * \text{gas density} * \text{gas length} / \text{energy per ion pair}$
- | | [eV m ² /kg] | [kg/m ³] | [m] | [eV] | |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------|----------------------|-----|------|-------|
| example: 10 MeV protons in 1 cm air | 1400 | 4e6 | 1.2 | 0.01 | 34.23 |
- stopping power: <http://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/Star/Text/PSTAR.html>

- saturation effects only at higher beam current densities, (but signal still increasing)
- charge collection time $t_{\text{coll}} = (\text{gap})^2 * (\text{high voltage})^{-1} * k^{-1}$
- example: gap 10 mm, high voltage 300 V
mobility of air $k_{\text{air}} \sim 1.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1} \rightarrow t_{\text{coll}} = 2 \text{ ms}$
- faster if only electrons used for signal („Frisch-grid chamber“, nitrogen filled, $t_{\text{coll}} \sim \mu\text{s}$)
- low energy limit: penetration of window
example: 50 μm Ti → protons of 2.8 MeV

Dölling, DIPAC05, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/d05/PAPERS/TTTA02.PDF>
@ homogeneous proton irradiation of full chamber

proportional chamber

- signal additionally enhanced by electron avalanche amplification by $\sim 10^4$
- amplification dependent on beam current density \rightarrow non-linear
- gas flow needed

gas electron multiplier (GEM)

front: ionisation chamber
 gas, e. g. Ar (70%) CO₂ (30%)
 middle: 1-3 GEM foils
 rear: strip pattern 1D or 2x 1D or pixels

- signal additionally enhanced by electron avalanche by 10² – 10⁵ depending of number of GEMs

- less discharges with more GEMs
- amplification not dependent on beam current density
 → linear (at not too high current densities)
- radiation hard
- gas flow needed

electron avalanche
 in high electric field
 in holes

pictures from Gas Detectors Development Group, CERN, <http://gdd.web.cern.ch/GDD/>

The first external cyclotron beam, obtained on March 26, 1936. The glow arises from the ionization of the air by the 5.8 MeV deuterons.

http://imglib.lbl.gov/LBNL_Res_Revs/RR_online/81F/81fchp2.html

in air: deuterons stopped after half a meter

↓
scaled by 10^{-9} in pressure (10^{-6} mbar)

in residual gas:

distance earth – moon (i. e. non-destructive)

very faint glow

beam induced fluorescence (BIF)

picture from
Forck, JUAS2009

- detectors

ICCD or EMCCD

multichannel PMT

scanning PMT

TV camera

Becker, DIPAC11, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/DIPAC2011/papers/weod01.pdf>

Becker et al., BIW08, <http://www-bd.gsi.de/uploads/paper/TUPTPF054.pdf>

Jung, DIPAC99, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d99/papers/CT12.pdf>

Plum et al., LHC Emittance Workshop (2000), see below

Dietrich et al., EPAC08, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e08/papers/tupc022.pdf>

Rezzonico et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum. 67(1996)1246-8

Joho et al., PAC1985 http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p85/PDF/PAC1985_2666.PDF

Chamberlin et al. PAC1981 http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p81/PDF/PAC1981_2347.PDF

- cross sections energy dependent (Bethe-Bloch) → easier at low energy

Plum et al., Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A 492 (2002) 74–90

Plum et al., LHC Emittance Workshop (2000),

<http://emittanceworkshop.web.cern.ch/EmittanceWorkshop/Slides%20M.Plum/GSPM.pdf> (link not valid)

- spectral components

Becker et al., DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tupb02.pdf>

BIW10, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/BIW2010/papers/tupsm020.pdf>

Ausset et al. EPAC02, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e02/PAPERS/THPRI066.pdf>

- distortion & limited dynamic range by

background radiation, delayed deexcitation (in helium gas) & reflections

1D-detector for residual gas ions
(strip pattern & current measurement
or MCP + CCD or ...)

- profile broadened by beam space charge (improved by vertical magnetic field & detecting electrons)
- non-destructive but eventual beam space charge neutralisation disturbed by external electric field
- sensitive

Kamerzhiev, DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tupb12.pdf>

DeLuca, PAC69, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p69/PDF/PAC1969_0813.PDF

residual gas ions (with beam space charge field)

Dölling et al., DIPAC99, LINAC96,
ICIS97: Rev. Sci. Instrum.69 (1998) 1094-9

Arauzo et al., NIMA 461 (2001) 111-114

- beam ion distribution creates residual gas ions & accelerating potential
- a positive beam potential depth of at least a few V is required
- analytical solution for charge density distribution of round non-neutralized beams
- non-destructive
- distortion of signal by charging of surfaces & stray magnetic fields

Dölling, DIPAC99,
<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d99/papers/CT02.pdf>

Gross et al, EPAC1990,
http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e90/PDF/EPAC1990_0806.PDF

„re-invented“ several times:

Garscadden et al., J. Electron. Contr. 9 (1960) 473

Harp et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum. 36 (1965) 960

Shiloh et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum., 54 (1983) 46

Shestak et al., Triumpf Design Note TRI-DN-87-36 (1987)

Prabir et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum. 76 (2005) 023301

and many others

- beam space charge potential deflects transversal electron beam
- deflection depending on impact parameter is measured
- analytical solution for charge density distribution of round beams (Abel inversion) [Stallings, J. Appl. Phys. 42 \(1971\) 2831](#)
- a positive beam potential depth of at least a few V is required
- non-destructive
- charging of surfaces and stray magnetic fields can be problematic
 - higher electron energy (→ less sensitivity) e. g. 75 keV [Aleksandrov et al., DIPAC09, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tuoa03.pdf](#)
 - ions [Bossler et al., CERN/PS 2000-071, http://cdsweb.cern.ch/record/478698/files/ps-2000-071.ps.gz](#)

C) diagnostics along the beam path

most examples from PSI's high power proton facility

+ external examples

which operates ~4800 h/a for ~400 users/a

- Injector 2 cyclotron**
- high beam current
 - separated sectors
 - normal conducting
- some space for diagnostics

spallation neutron source SING since 1998
(liquid Pb-Bi target during 2006)

581 MeV
1.5 mA
0.9 MW

0.87 MeV protons
10 mA DC,
10 kW

Injector 2 cyclotron

72 MeV
2.2 mA
160 kW CW

0.06 mA
isotope production

Ring cyclotron since 1974

590 MeV
2.2 mA
1.3 MW
CW (50MHz)

radial probe

meson production targets

~4 s pulses to UCN every 400 s from 2011

ion source & injection line:

matching the beam core to the cyclotron acceptance

beam position, profile, current

60 keV LEBT, 2 solenoids
~fully space-charge compensated
27 mA extracted
 H_2^+ , H_3^+ stopped at collimators

870 keV transport, magnetic quadrupoles
~50% (?) space-charge compensated
~10.6 mA protons at entrance
~1.6 mA cut at ~30 (fixed) collimators → beam shaping

Markovits, PAC 1987

profile monitors

calorimetric slit scanner
(at 60 keV, destructive)

Olivo, CYC87 p. 519

- internal cooled copper block behind vertical slit
- measurement of water in-/outlet temperatures

wire scanner
(870 keV 11 mA
up to 20% DC)

Rezzonico, CYC87 p. 457

motor

worm gear
crank
con-rod

pendulum axis

wire or foil
(isolated)

beam induced fluorescence
monitor
(870 keV full beam
non-destructive)

PMT and lens scanned

Photo-multiplier

Slit

Stepping Motor

Lens

Glass Vacuum Window

Beam

80

380 mm

profile monitors

for high
beam power

calorimetric slit scanner
(at 60 keV, destructive)

- internal cooled copper block behind vertical slit
- measurement of water in-/outlet temperatures

beam induced fluorescence monitor
(870 keV full beam non-destructive)

PMT and lens scanned

direct emittance measurement

- destructive, limited in beam power & energy

moving slit + grid

moving line of holes + screen

more information
than slit + grid

+ many other configurations

(pepperpot, Allison-scanner, ...)

http://adweb.desy.de/mdi/CARE/Bad_Kreuznach/Reports/ABI-Workshop_Proceedings_all.pdf

profile based emittance measurement

- input only 3 beam widths \rightarrow less information

3-profile method

for high
beam power
or high
energy

Q-pole variation method

Braun, CAS2008

needs „beam gymnastics“ \rightarrow difficult for high power beams

test stand simulates cyclotron center
with internal source
including magnetic field
and fixed puller voltage/geometry:

emittance of internal ion source [MSU]

numerical simulation
for different plasma pressures:

Measurement of radial emittance

slit – wire emittance measurement
for radial emittance:

(similar for axial emittance)

all figures from E. R. Forringer, Dissertation 2004, MSU
http://www.nslc.msu.edu/ourlab/publications/download/Forringer_2004_199.pdf

collimators with current readout

- help to „guide“ the beam through the machine
- protect the machine by interlock generation
- shape the beam (this may need cooling)

sputtered material
(earlier) short-cuttet
current measurement
→ no interlock
→ melts in ~1 s
at missteered beam
(cooling would not
have prevented it)

injection, central region

beam shaping & betatron oscillation alignment

current set & beam shaping

- by cutting into beam with movable cooled collimators with current measurement (no activation below a few MeV)
 - (current set combined with phase selection, dominates „injection efficiency, ~13 kW)
- again: collimators help to „guide“ the beam and to protect the machine
- stopper allows to set up central region alone at full current (~10 kW)

beam centering & betatron oscillation alignment

- beam „positions“ at full current: known only from collimator currents, at low current: from radial probe
- vertical centering with vertical adjustments
- horizontal betatron oscillations around the centered path adjusted with horizontal adjustments

acceleration:

adjustment of magnetic field and RF fields

adjustment of magnetic field for isochronous acceleration

full beam (2300 uA)

MIF - Phasenmessung Nr. 2846 - 09

Mini-Save

MIF-Phasenmessung

Datum: 2009.09.30 Zeit: 11:43:27

Trimmspul-Werte

Messung	Fit-Wert
T11	-10
T12	350
T13	-882
T14	-1134
T15	-1200
T16	-808
T17	-63
T18	383
T19	882
T110	1086
T111	-600
AIHS	1948
	2001

M. Humbel, PSI

from „phase history“

- correction of (drifting) **main field** (recommended in this example)
- correction of **trim coil** settings

operates at 2nd harmonic

variant: improved sensitivity by intensity modulation of the beam
 Brandenburg et al., DIPAC03,
<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/d03/papers/PT12.pdf>

beam centering & betatron oscillation alignment

finding the beam and „pulling“ it to greater radii

- horizontal adjustment (trim coils, electrostatic septum, septum magnet)
- accelerating gaps
- phase probes, time structure probe
- radial probes

beam centering & betatron oscillation alignment

long radial probe

only 1 uA beam

RIL1 Messung Nr. 1-92 Bereich: 511mm bis 1511mm
 RIL1-Innenmessung. 4% gepulst Datum: 2-MAR-92 Zeit: 04:22:44

Pseudo Tomographie (skaliert mit 1.0)

vertical

Mini-Save

EWBRV	810.77kV	DAC
EVEK	59.96kV	DAC
AIMS	55800	DAC
AIMS	2288	FEIN
TI1	1800	DAC
TI2	2000	DAC
TI3	-450	DAC
TI4	-450	DAC
TI5	-450	DAC
TI6	-400	DAC
TI7	-300	DAC
TI8	350	DAC
TI9	700	DAC
TI10	250	DAC
TI11	300	DAC
CI1V	52000	DAC
CI2V	0	DAC
CI3V	47410	DAC
CI4V	0	DAC
CIPHFT	1600	DAC
AWDX	1.60mm	DAC
TI1DIFF	500	DAC
TIK	-1000	DAC
KIP2	405.38mm	DAC
KIP4L	598.06mm	DAC
KIP4R	611.02mm	DAC
AWD1	0.01mm	DAC
AWD	61340	DAC
EIV1V	-100	DAC
EIV2V	40	DAC
A	-1.07mm	DAC
B	0.63mm	DAC
C	0.19mm	DAC
D	-2.10mm	DAC
Turn DAC	91.87	DAC

intentionally introduced radial betatron oscillations

beam centering & betatron oscillation alignment

long radial probe

only 1 uA beam

RIL1 Messung Nr. 29 - 07

Strahlqualitaet

Bereich: 515mm bis 3514mm

Datum: 2007.04.25 Zeit: 03:49:14

Turn DAC 81.94
Turn ADC 81.10

Radien von Finger Nr. 2

542.46	614.80	673.60	736.20	808.60	872.60	913.60	940.00	1022.60	1076.00
1110.20	1152.80	1212.00	1258.80	1288.40	1332.60	1389.60	1425.60	1455.60	1507.20
1555.60	1582.20	1619.60	1674.00	1702.40	1733.00	1783.60	1826.00	1848.20	1888.40
1938.80	1964.00	1992.20	2043.20	2075.00	2095.40	2141.60	2181.20	2199.80	2267.60
2392.00	2400.00	2331.20	2378.40	2398.80	2424.00	2471.20	2495.40	2515.80	2560.00
2584.60	2602.60	2647.60	2672.80	2689.60	2732.80	2759.80	2774.80	2815.60	2844.40
2858.20	2897.20	2924.20	2957.40	2974.40	2972.80	3011.40	3015.40	3054.40	3077.20
3130.00	3151.20	3165.80	3204.20	3222.20	3238.80	3276.20	3292.20	3308.60	3345.60
3358.80									

Mini-Save

EWBRV	811.87	kV
EVEX	60.00	kV
AIHS	55840	DAC
AIHS	2940	DAC
TI1	140	DAC
TI2	880	DAC
TI3	-680	DAC
TI4	-975	DAC
TI5	-1043	DAC
TI6	-800	DAC
TI7	-150	DAC
TI8	243	DAC
TI9	788	DAC
TI10	1043	DAC
TI11	43	DAC
C1V	49290	DAC
C2V	38800	DAC
C3V	49921	DAC
C4V	38800	DAC
CIPHFT	1720	DAC
AWDX	1.52	mm
TI1DIFF	140	DAC
TIK	-1550	DAC
KIP2	413.42	mm
KIP4L	407.86	mm
KIP4R	612.74	mm
AWDY	1.97	mm
AWD	60990	DAC
EIV1V	-340	DAC
EIV2V	0	DAC

intentionally introduced radial betatron oscillations (only vertical wire displayed)

turn counting

RIL 1 Messung Nr. 67 - 07

Strahlqualitaet

Bereich: 515mm bis 3514mm

Datum: 2007.04.25 Zeit: 17:37:14

Turn DAC 80.65
Turn ADC 79.94

Mini-Save

Radien von Finger Nr. 2

538.00	610.00	682.80	750.80	811.80	869.20	923.20	977.80	1028.80	1075.40
1123.40	1173.00	1218.00	1262.80	1307.60	1352.20	1395.20	1437.80	1480.40	1522.40
1562.20	1604.60	1645.80	1685.40	1725.60	1764.80	1803.00	1841.40	1880.40	1918.20
1953.80	1991.00	2026.40	2062.40	2099.20	2133.00	2169.00	2203.60	2237.80	2270.40
2305.80	2369.60	2402.20	2434.80	2467.20	2499.80	2527.80	2558.20	2589.80	2617.00
2650.20	2679.20	2710.00	2737.60	2766.80	2796.20	2824.60	2851.80	2880.00	2906.00
2932.40	2959.80	2987.40	3012.60	3046.40	3080.80	3114.00	3142.20	3167.40	3191.40
3218.60	3240.40	3268.20	3311.40	3355.20	3399.20	3479.80			

EWBRV	811.87	kV
EVEX	60.00	kV
AIHS	55844	DAC
AIHS	2910	DAC
TI1	140	DAC
TI2	888	DAC
TI3	-600	DAC
TI4	-975	DAC
TI5	-1043	DAC
TI6	-800	DAC
TI7	-150	DAC
TI8	243	DAC
TI9	788	DAC
TI10	1043	DAC
TI11	43	DAC
C11V	49290	DAC
C12V	38804	DAC
C13V	51787	DAC
C14V	38800	DAC
CIPHFT	1720	DAC
AWDX	1.98	mm
TI1DIFF	2330	DAC
TIK	-1000	DAC
KIP2	4.11.65	mm
KIP4L	402.83	mm
KIP4R	623.31	mm
AWDY	1.98	mm
AWD	60990	DAC
EIV1V	-340	DAC
EIV2V	0	DAC

radial betatron oscillations eliminated temporarily for turn counting (only vertical wire displayed)

alternative (also for not separated turns):

- measurement of modulated beam (maybe from ion source noise)
- with phase probes before and after the cyclotron
- cross correlation → time of flight

Craddock et al., CYC75, p. 240

Loyer et al., PAC1985, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/p85/PDF/PAC1985_1938.PDF

M. Humbel, PSI

extraction:

turn separation & efficiency

turn separation

D. Götz, PSI

3 strips with current measurement

septum foils between the last 2 turns

as few as possible beam should hit the foils in order to prevent beam loss !

turn separation

full beam
(2300 uA)
only vertical
finger shown

extraction
probe 2

RIE2 Messung Nr. 23 - 09

Bereich: 3199mm bis 3349mm Datum: 2009.09.30 Zeit: 11:40:49

RSP [mm]	3233.5	3249.1	3270.3	3318.1
4σ	13.7	14.5	14.2	14.3

square indicates
sine & cosine
components of
horizontal
betatron oscillation

„empirically
good“

valley

Strahlqualitaet

BRAV	14.19	mm
Verlust	54.800	nA
Turn DAC	81.62	
Puls 1 :	1.00	

Zentrierung

RO	3301.94	mm
DR	23.25	mm
EF	-3.08	
FF	4.75	

Mini-Save

EWBRV	44120	DAC
CIPHFT	1900	DAC
MXC1	2302.20	uA
MWC2	10.48	uA
KIDE	-0.01	uA
KXA 11	0.13	uA
AIHS	1948	FEIN
KIP2	399.02	mm
RIL2	534.69	mm
KIP4L	605.77	mm
KIP4R	614.84	mm
T11	-10	DAC
SWV11X	1150	DAC
AWDX	1.10	mm
TIK	40	DAC
T11DIFF	210	DAC
C11V	49280	DAC
C12V	39240	DAC
C13V	51337	DAC
C14V	33550	DAC
CIPHFT	1900	DAC

Rezzonico et al., BIW1994

horizontal betatron oscillation tuned for

- large separation of last turn at extraction elements
- nearly 100% extraction efficiency = low losses

halo measurement with 10⁴ dynamic range

turn separation

full beam
(2300 uA)
only vertical
finger shown

extraction
probe 1

RIE1 Messung Nr. 132 - 02

Bereich: 3198mm bis 3397mm Datum: 18-MAR-02 Zeit: 07:50:33

RSP [mm] 4σ

increasing beam current

Strahlqualiaet

BRV	10.00 mm
Verlust	48.88 nA
Turn DAC	85.81
Puls 1	1.00
Beam	100.00% on DC
Res.	2+4 150.00 MHz ein

Zentrierung

Ro	3356.00 mm
DR	22.50 mm
E	-0.00 mm
F	0.00 mm

Mini-Save

EWBRV	58982	DAC
CIPHFT	1650	DAC
MXC 1	1090.00 uA	
MWC 2	12.20 mA	
KXA 1I	-0.00 uA	
AHS	24.10 FEIN	
KIP2	300.00 mm	
MITR	20.00%	
RIL 2	521.53 mm	
KIP4L	600.10 mm	
KIP4R	610.78 mm	
CWBV	1230	DAC
CWBPH	43	DAC
CWBPHF	1965	DAC
TI 1	299	DAC
TI 2	600	DAC
SWV 11X	1040	DAC
AWDX	1.50 mm	
TIK	-2400	DAC
TI 1DIFF	400	DAC
CI 1V	49500	DAC
CI 2V	27800	DAC
CI 3V	48820	DAC
CI 4V	27800	DAC

M. Humbel, PSI

developing valley for extraction elements
unchanged by beam current variation
(accomplished by cutting the beam single-
sided with a collimator in the machine center)
→ good extraction efficiency at all currents

D) transversal information (in cyclotron):
radial probes at high / low current

radial probes: types and uses

- radial: integral (thick) or differential

- axial: segmentation / tomography

schematic

radial probes: types and uses

integral + differential probe
at separated turns

probe efficiency < 1
visible only when turn is cut

losses
extraction efficiency

turn structure

GANIL NCO1 injector, Ricaud et al., CYC92 p. 446

radial probes: types and uses

integral probe at **not** separated turns

shadow method

- ~ turn profile
- ampl. incoherent betatron oscill. (from shadow width)

50% method

- centering (centered if probe radii identical at crossover)

Schematic diagram showing the principle of LE1-LE2 shadow measurement. ν_r is assumed to be $\simeq 1.0$. (a) a fraction of a beam spot hits on N^{th} turn, the missing portion hits on $(N + 1)^{\text{th}}$ turn; (b) expected variations of beam current on LE1 and LE2 as LE1 moves across the beam paths.

Figure 11: Measured beam currents on LE1 and LE2 vs the radial position of LE1, with LE2 parked at different radii. Shown on the top are the beam distributions along the radius. The data at ~ 69 inch clearly shows that beam hitting LE2 is coming from 2 turns.

from Rao et al., TRI-DN-04-8,
<http://legacyweb.triumf.ca/publications/pub/dn/2004/TRI-DN-04-08.pdf>
 see also Schreuder, NIM 95 (1971) p. 237

radial probes: types and uses

integral probes: efficiency depends on impact angle

here: in mid-range efficiency $\ll 1$

→ behaviour similar to differential probe

probe measures turn density

radial betatron oscillations visible

→ information on radial beam centering

at low & high energies: full beam stopped

→ behaves as integral probe

→ extraction efficiency

PSI's medical cyclotron (Varian, 250 MeV, compact), Geisler et al., CYC07 talk, see also <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/c07/PAPERS/9.PDF>

good radial centering

simulation

Schippers, CYC04 talk, see also http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/c04/data/CYC2004_papers/21A3.pdf

radial probes: types and uses / signal

integral probes: efficiency depends on impact angle

here: in mid-range efficiency $\ll 1$

→ behaviour similar to differential probe

probe measures turn density

radial betatron oscillations visible

→ information on radial beam centering

at low & high energies: full beam stopped

→ behaves as integral probe

→ extraction efficiency

simulation

PSI's medical cyclotron (Varian, 250 MeV, compact), Geisler et al., CYC07 talk, see also <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/c07/PAPERS/9.PDF>

bad
radial
centering

Schippers, CYC04 talk, see also http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/c04/data/CYC2004_papers/21A3.pdf

secondary electron capture
(also: bias or pulling electrode)

TRIUMF, Craddock et al., CYC75 p. 240

UCLA 50 MeV, Clark et al., CYC62 p. 1

radial probes: high current

thermal limits at high current

size limitation
→ power limitation
~15 kW protons

power input maximal
if beam particle just stopped
→ difficult at low energies (few MeV)
and heavier beam particles

thin carbon fibres have highest performance
but give small electrical signal

alternatives?

The layout inside the vacuum chamber of SPC1. Components that can be seen are the first slit system, electrostatic- and first magnetic channel, ion source (slightly withdrawn) and, to the left of the dee in the foreground, the ionisation beam profile monitor.

signal level OK at 10^{-6} mbar
(amplification by e.g. MCP not needed)

dynamic range?

- probably determined by stray particles
- probably <1000

(later abandoned due to isolation problems from sputtering in machine center)

Beam profile of an internal beam (orbits 12 and 13) as recorded on the ionisation beam profile monitor installed in the pole-gap of SPC1.

beam induced fluorescence

single PMT

PSI, Rezzonico, CYC87 p. 457

32 channel PMT

iTHEMBA injection line,
Dietrich et al., EPAC08,
<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/e08/papers/tupc022.pdf>

MCP + CCD

GSI, Forck, IPAC10,
<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/IPAC10/html/author.htm>

all used in beam lines

- (less signal than RGI)
- dynamic range?
determined by stray light
at best ~500

in the cyclotron?

- disturbing light
- radiation hard & sensitive camera?
or relay optic
- PMT/MCP magnetic shielding?

viewer probe

Figure 1. Sketch showing the head of the TV probe. The angle the beam makes with the scintillating plate changes between 35 and 65 degrees.

MSU, Marti et al., CYC92 p. 435

also (since long):
with external observation

thin paper burn

IBA, Kleeven, CYC01, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/c01/cyc2001/paper/L-1.pdf>

Figure 12: Beam spots in the central region

also (for commissioning):

Kapton, Mylar,
stainless steel
track-etch foil
radiochromic film
radiographic film
foil activation
radiography

E) longitudinal information (in cyclotron)

(usually resonance curve shown at fixed radius, main field varied)

here: at multi-head radial probe (usually: fixed pickups)

both pictures
D. Fourie, iTHEMBA

- can deliver
- center phase (very accurate)
- time structure
- (not for very short bunches)

can deliver
local phase width
around center phase

silicon detector placed directly in very low current beam

silicon detector
on radial probe (shield removed)

probe head with shield & preamplifier

can deliver

- time structure (moderate resolution)
- beam particle energy spectrum (thick detector)
- beam particle stopping power (thin detector)

all pictures F. Chautard, GANIL

cyclotron separates different particles by q/m

time-structure shows separation (radius varied)

Diagnostics
exotiques
de CIME

Chautard et al., CYC01, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/c01/cyc2001/paper/P4-17.pdf>

particle species identified by energy
(although time-structure overlaps)

GANIL Report 03-02 p. 21

probe at fixed radius

based on scattered protons:

- measure longitudinal and radial density distributions of the beam bunches (averaging over many bunches)
- arrival time of scattered protons compared to RF reference (discriminator & Time-to-Ampl. Converter & Multi-Channel-Analyzer)
- resolution incl. electronics ~31 ps fwhm (determined from correlation between detectors A, B)

Dölling, HB10, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/HB2010/papers/mopd62.pdf>

simple estimate of time resolution of detector B

PMT transit time spread (TTS)	250 ps	(R7400)
scintillator response	1360 ps	(NE111)
path in scintillator	400 ps	

$$dt = 1.2 \sqrt{\frac{250^2 + 1360^2 + 400^2}{5500}} = 23 \text{ ps fwhm}$$

(much faster with RF-deflection of secondary electrons from biased wire)

Feschenko et al., LINAC86, p. 323

Feschenko et al., PAC01, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e90/PDF/EPAC1990_0750.PDF

Bylinsky et al., EPAC94, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e94/PDF/EPAC1994_1702.PDF

Feschenko et al., PAC07, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p07/PAPERS/THOAA01.PDF>

Aleksandrov et al., BIW12, MOPE041

2.3 mA proton beam, moving bunches as seen from above
→ detailed input to beam dynamic simulations

F) beam losses & beam halo

beam losses: „protection aspect“

- activation
- melting of cyclotron components by missteered (high power) beam
→ fast interlock generation needed (~1 ms)

collimators

with current readout

injection into Ring cyclotron:

collimator and coil support destroyed

(defect of high level interlock module)

590 MeV, 2.2 mA, 1.3 MW, $t_{\text{melt}} = 10 \text{ ms}$

beam losses: „protection aspect“

ionization chambers

- most simple variant: ambient air filled, 300 V
- useful at beam energies >40 MeV \rightarrow proton range in steel > 3 mm
- placed $\sim 0.1 \dots 1$ m from beam, fixed position for reproducibility
- approximate calibration by steering low current beam into wall

- radiation induced attenuation of optical fibers (range few kGy, position resolution ~1 m)

Wulf, Körfer, DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/weoa01.pdf>

(Roughly) Estimated Sensitivities

linear in used range,
very radiation hard

- Ionization chamber:** **70 μC/Gy**
 1 liter argon
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{charge per ionization energy} \approx V \cdot \rho \cdot e / E_{\text{ion}} \approx 1 \text{ l} \cdot 1.8 \text{ g/l} \cdot e / 26 \text{ eV}$
- Long ionization chamber:** **20 μC/Gy**
 1 meter length, 1 cm radius, argon
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{charge per ionization energy} \approx \pi r^2 \cdot L \cdot \rho \cdot e / E_{\text{ion}} \approx 314 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot 1.8 \text{ g/l} \cdot e / 26 \text{ eV}$
- PIN diode:** **6 μC/Gy**
 1 cm² surface, 100 μm depletion depth
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{charge per excitation energy} \approx A \cdot d \cdot \rho \cdot e / E_{\text{ion}} \approx 10 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot 2.3 \text{ g/cm}^3 \cdot e / 3.6 \text{ eV}$
- Secondary emission monitor:** **500 pC/Gy**
 100 cm² surface, 0.01 average secondary emission yield (SEY)
 $S \approx \text{surface} \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot \text{electron charge} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \approx A \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot e \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx))$
 $\approx 100 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot 0.01 \cdot e \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g})$
- Aluminum cathode electron multiplier:** **5 μC/Gy**
 10 cm² surface, 0.01 average secondary emission yield (SEY), tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{surface} \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot \text{electron charge} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \cdot \text{gain} \approx A \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot e \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx)) \cdot G$
 $\approx 10 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot 0.01 \cdot e \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g}) \cdot 10^5$
- PMT with organic scintillator:** **200 C/Gy**
 1 liter scintillator, 60% collection efficiency, 30% photocathode efficiency, tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{photon yield per energy} \cdot \text{collection efficiency} \cdot \text{photocathode efficiency} \cdot \text{gain} \cdot \text{electron charge}$
 $\approx V \cdot \rho \cdot Y \cdot C \cdot P \cdot G \cdot e = 1 \text{ l} \cdot 1 \text{ g/cm}^3 \cdot 1 / (100 \text{ eV}) \cdot 0.6 \cdot 0.3 \cdot 10^5 \cdot e$
- Bare PMT (Čerenkov light):** **4 mC/Gy**
 10 cm² surface, 1 mm thick, 30% photocathode efficiency, tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{active volume} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \cdot \text{photon yield per length} \cdot \text{photocath. efficiency} \cdot \text{gain} \cdot \text{electron charge}$
 $\approx A \cdot d \cdot \rho \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx)) \cdot Y \cdot P \cdot G \cdot e \approx 1 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g}) \cdot 260/\text{cm} \cdot 0.3 \cdot 10^5 \cdot e$
- PMT with Čerenkov fiber:** **2 μC/Gy**
 1 meter length, 100 μm radius, 2% collection efficiency, 30% photocathode eff., tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{active volume} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \cdot \text{photon yield per length} \cdot \text{coll. eff.} \cdot \text{photoc. eff.} \cdot \text{gain} \cdot \text{electron charge}$
 $\approx \pi r^2 \cdot L \cdot \rho \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx)) \cdot Y \cdot C \cdot P \cdot G \cdot e \approx 31 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g}) \cdot 260/\text{cm} \cdot 0.02 \cdot 0.3 \cdot 10^5 \cdot e$

linear even at
very high dose rate,
very radiation hard

Radiation damage problematic!

very sensitive

only for relativistic particles (β>0.68)

Flexible gain → linearity and calibration problematic!

beam losses & beam halo: „knowledge aspect“

„empirical tuning“ has its limits:

- losses lead to activation, this limits the beam current (personal dose at maintenance)
- to prevent losses, the beam halo must be cut or matched through all the machine (some controlled loss in shielded locations allowed)
- it is difficult to measure and simulate the beam halo (new halo by scattering at collimators, ...)
- hence empirical tuning is used („turn all available knobs“) based on collimator/loss monitor readings
- „knowledge aspect“ diagnostics only needed at trouble („what is different than yesterday?“)

-
- delivers optimum for *given* machine configuration
 - cannot suggest *changes* of machine configuration for improvement
 - difficult to find hidden causes in case of persistantly bad beam quality

→ detailed beam dynamic simulations needed for progress („a real understanding of losses“)

depiction of changes of collimator currents and lossmonitor readings used for „empirical“ tuning

A. Mezger, PSI

detailed numerical simulations

- including beam halo, scattering at collimators, 3D-poisson solver, space charge neutralisation
- lead to a better understanding of the losses: *where* (at low energies) *to cut and how to match the halo*
- a very high dynamic range is needed: every 10 nA of beam losses are important
- fitting capabilities needed in order to find the best fit to a large set of detailed profile & loss data (detailed information on quality/error has to be provided with each measurement)
- very encouraging work is in progress:

simulation of 3 mA in Ring cyclotron including neighboring turns

simulation of turn-pattern at exit of Ring cyclotron

Bi et al., CYC10, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/Cyclotrons2010/papers/mopcp045.pdf>

Yang et al., Phys. Rev. ST Accel. Beams 13, 064201 (2010)

input from beam diagnostics to *detailed* simulations of beam losses

- losses are measured with large dynamic range
 - at collimators (limited by stray particles)
 - with loss monitors

but spatial resolution is usually modest

- transverse and longitudinal profiles (1D, 2D)
- emittance (2D, 4D)

accuracy and dynamic range have limits

actually it is not really clear what the requirements to precision/resolution/dynamic range of measurements are in this context

(requirements need to be evaluated by simulations)

are „future losses“ visible in a projected 1D profile?

- at a high current beam (2 mA) a relevant loss (~10 nA) is a beam fraction of 5×10^{-6}
- in a projected 1D profile (e.g. from a wire scanner) a dynamic range of $\sim 10^6$ is needed to see the 10 nA compared to the 2 mA (of course the loss particles are only visible if located in the halo and not in the beam core)
- in beam lines (low background & stray particles) this is feasible for wire scanners using detection of scattered particles and maybe even with direct wire current measurement
- example of purposely caused losses with known origin, which change the beam profile:

Detection of beam ions, scattered ~ 20 m upstream by a 33 μm carbon fibre placed in the beam, with two vertical wire scanners in front of the Ring cyclotron. The beam losses in Ring cyclotron are increased by the order of 100 nA. (This is qualitative because the logarithmic current amplifiers are too slow compared to wire speed at currents below a 3×10^{-4} level.)

(we need to improve this by a factor of 10 to 100)

in the cyclotrons this is much more difficult (high background & stray particles)

→ separate measurement of beam core and halo

Thanks for listening!

at high currents:

- DC/AC current transformers

Denard, CAS2008, <http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/France-2008/Lectures/Denard.pdf>
 Webber, Proc. AccApp'07 p. 145-151

- resonant cavity [Reimann, Rüede, NIM 129 \(1975\) 53-58](#)

at low currents:

- Cryogenic Current Comparator

Vodel et al., DIPAC2007, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d07/papers/wepb30.pdf>

- thin SEMs or ionisation chambers (scattering!)

example:

ionisation chamber behind PSIs medical cyclotron

Dölling et al., Proc. AccApp'07 p. 152-159

measures current fluctuations from the internal ion source

Schippers et al., CYC07, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/c07/PAPERS/300.PDF>

beam current and its noise

6 μm titanium foils
soldered to
thick-film coated
ceramic frames

thin SEM or ionisation chamber behind PSIs medical cyclotron

used for proton beam 250 MeV

IC: in a N_2 filled box
with thin Ti-windows
signal amplified by 43
thermal limit: 1 μA beam

SEM: in vacuum
signal „amplified“ by 0.053
microphonics